

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

RESEARCH ON THE PROPERTIES AND APPLICATIONS OF VANDERMONDE DETERMINANT

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ABSTRACT

Determinant is an important component of modern linear algebra and has wide-ranging applications in mathematics and related disciplines. This paper first systematically introduces the relevant knowledge of Vandermonde determinant, including its definition, result, properties, and the proof method based on elimination. On this basis, it focuses on discussing the application value and problem-solving techniques of Vandermonde determinant in multiple mathematical branches. The specific application fields include determinant calculation, vector space theory, polynomial theory, and calculus. Research shows that due to its unique form and concise calculation result, Vandermonde determinant can solve complex mathematical problems with high-level techniques, reflecting the integration of knowledge.

Keywords: Vandermonde determinant; polynomial; vector space theory; calculus.

1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Linear algebra is one of the two pillars of modern mathematics, and its theories and methods have extensive and significant applications in numerous fields such as natural sciences, engineering technology, and economic management. As a core concept of linear algebra, determinants are not only key tools for solving linear systems of equations and judging the linear dependence of vector sets, but their special structural forms also embody rich mathematical properties.

Among various special determinants, the Vandermonde determinant stands out due to its concise structure and definite calculation results. This unique characteristic enables the Vandermonde determinant to play an irreplaceable role in fields such as advanced algebra, polynomial interpolation, and coding theory.

2 Vandermonde Determinant

2.1 Definition of the Vandermonde Determinant

We refer to a determinant of the form

$$D_n = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_1^{n-1} & x_2^{n-1} & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & x_1 & \cdots & 1^{n-1} \\ 1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_2^{n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_n & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \end{vmatrix}$$

as a Vandermonde determinant.

2.2 Properties of the Vandermonde Determinant

Property 1: Rotating a Vandermonde determinant counterclockwise by 90° results in

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & x_n & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \\ 1 & x_{n-1} & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_1 & \cdots & x_1^{n-1} \end{vmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{Transpose}} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ x_n & x_{n-1} & \cdots & x_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_n^{n-1} & x_{n-1}^{n-1} & \cdots & x_1^{n-1} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\xrightarrow{\text{Exchange each column}} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_1^{n-1} & x_2^{n-1} & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \end{vmatrix} \cdot (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} = (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \cdot D_n.$$

1.2 Research Significance

Although the basic theory of the Vandermonde determinant has been introduced in advanced algebra textbooks, it is still necessary to conduct in-depth exploration of its properties and systematic summary of its application techniques. Especially when solving complex mathematical problems, how to quickly and accurately identify, transform, and apply the conclusions of the Vandermonde determinant is the key to improving problem-solving efficiency.

This paper aims to systematically sort out the definition, properties, and proof methods of the Vandermonde determinant, and through specific case analyses, demonstrate its application value and advanced problem-solving techniques in multiple mathematical branches such as determinant calculation, vector space theory, polynomial theory, and calculus.

Property 2: Rotating a Vandermonde determinant counterclockwise by 180° results in

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{vmatrix} x_n^{n-1} & x_{n-1}^{n-1} & \cdots & x_1^{n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_n & x_{n-1} & \cdots & x_1 \\ 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \end{vmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{Exchange each row } (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{n}}} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ x_n & x_{n-1} & \cdots & x_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_n^{n-1} & x_{n-1}^{n-1} & \cdots & x_1^{n-1} \end{vmatrix} \\ & = (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{n}} \cdot (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{n}} D_n = D_n. \end{aligned}$$

Property 3: Rotating a Vandermonde determinant counterclockwise by 270° results in

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{vmatrix} x_1^{n-1} & x_1^{n-2} & \cdots & x_1 & 1 \\ x_2^{n-1} & x_2^{n-2} & \cdots & x_2 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_n^{n-1} & x_n^{n-2} & \cdots & x_n & 1 \end{vmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{Transpose}} \begin{vmatrix} x_1^{n-1} & x_2^{n-1} & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \\ x_1^{n-2} & x_2^{n-2} & \cdots & x_n^{n-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \\ & \xrightarrow{\text{Exchange each row } (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}} (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \cdot D_n. \end{aligned}$$

Property 4: Rotating a Vandermonde determinant counterclockwise by 360° results in $D = D_n$.

In summary, rotating a Vandermonde determinant counterclockwise by an odd multiple of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ results in D

$$= (-1)^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \cdot D_n; \text{rotating it by an even multiple of } \frac{\pi}{2} \text{ results in } D = D_n.$$

2.3 Proof of the Vandermonde Determinant

The n -th Order Vandermonde Determinant

$$D_n = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ x_1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_1^{n-1} & x_2^{n-1} & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & x_1 & \cdots & 1^{n-1} \\ 1 & x_2 & \cdots & x_2^{n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_n & \cdots & x_n^{n-1} \end{vmatrix} = \prod_{1 \leq j < i \leq n} (x_i - x_j).$$

Proof: The value of the Vandermonde determinant is derived using the "elimination method". Starting from the n -th row, add $-x_1$ times the previous row to each row. According to the properties of determinants, the value of the determinant remains unchanged. At this point, we can obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} D_n &= \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & x_2 - x_1 & \cdots & x_{n-1} - x_1 & x_n - x_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & x_2^{n-3}(x_2 - x_1) & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-3}(x_{n-1} - x_1) & x_n^{n-3}(x_n - x_1) \\ 0 & x_2^{n-2}(x_2 - x_1) & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-2}(x_{n-1} - x_1) & x_n^{n-2}(x_n - x_1) \end{vmatrix} \\ &= 1 \cdot \begin{vmatrix} x_2 - x_1 & \cdots & x_{n-1} - x_1 & x_n - x_1 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_2^{n-3}(x_2 - x_1) & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-3}(x_{n-1} - x_1) & x_n^{n-3}(x_n - x_1) \\ x_2^{n-2}(x_2 - x_1) & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-2}(x_{n-1} - x_1) & x_n^{n-2}(x_n - x_1) \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

factor out the common factor of each column

$$= (x_2 - x_1) \cdots (x_{n-1} - x_1)(x_n - x_1) \cdot \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 & 1 \\ x_2 & x_3 & \cdots & x_{n-1} & x_n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_2^{n-3} & x_3^{n-3} & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-3} & x_n^{n-3} \\ x_2^{n-2} & x_3^{n-2} & \cdots & x_{n-1}^{n-2} & x_n^{n-2} \end{vmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Note: The determinant in (1) is an $(n-1)$ -th order Vandermonde determinant D_{n-1} . We have expressed D_n in terms of D_{n-1} . By repeating the above process to solve for D_{n-1} , after a finite number of calculations, we can obtain:

$$D_n = ((x_2 - x_1) \cdots (x_{n-1} - x_1)(x_n - x_1))((x_3 - x_2) \cdots (x_{n-1} - x_2)(x_n - x_2)) \cdots (x_n - x_{n-1}) \\ = \prod_{1 \leq j < i \leq n} (x_i - x_j).$$

3 Applications of the Vandermonde Determinant

3.1 Applications of the Vandermonde Determinant in Determinant Calculation

Based on the structural characteristics and properties of the Vandermonde determinant, we can simplify the calculation of ordinary determinants. By converting some non-Vandermonde determinants into Vandermonde determinants using various methods, we can then compute them using the results of the Vandermonde determinant.

Example 1: Calculate

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + x_1 & 1 + x_1^2 & \cdots & 1 + x_1^n \\ 1 + x_2 & 1 + x_2^2 & \cdots & 1 + x_2^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 + x_n & 1 + x_n^2 & \cdots & 1 + x_n^n \end{vmatrix}.$$

Solution: This determinant can be calculated using the method of splitting rows (or columns). Specifically, the i -th row (or column) of D is composed of two sub-rows (or sub-columns), where any two adjacent rows (or columns) share the same sub-row (or sub-column); Furthermore, since D contains a Vandermonde determinant composed of n sub-rows (or sub-columns), we add -1 times the i -th row (or column) of D to the $i+1$ -th row (or column) to eliminate some sub-rows (or sub-columns), thereby converting D into a Vandermonde determinant.

First

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & 1 + x_1 & 1 + x_1^2 & \cdots & 1 + x_1^n \\ 1 & 1 + x_2 & 1 + x_2^2 & \cdots & 1 + x_2^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 + x_n & 1 + x_n^2 & \cdots & 1 + x_n^n \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -1 & -1 & \cdots & -1 \\ 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^n \\ 1 & x_2 & x_2^2 & \cdots & x_2^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & \cdots & x_n^n \end{vmatrix},$$

then split the 1st row into the sum of two terms, yielding

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & \cdots & x_n^n \end{vmatrix} - \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \\ 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & \cdots & x_n^n \end{vmatrix} \\ = 2x_1x_2 \cdots x_n \prod_{1 \leq j < k \leq n} (x_k - x_j) - \prod_{i=1}^n (x_i - 1) \prod_{1 \leq j < k \leq n} (x_k - x_j) \\ = \prod_{1 \leq j < k \leq n} (x_k - x_j) [2 \prod_{i=1}^n x_i - \prod_{i=1}^n (x_i - 1)].$$

3.2 Applications of the Vandermonde Determinant in Vector Space Theory

In the theory of vector spaces, we often encounter problems that require transformation using the Vandermonde determinant. Through such transformation, we can easily derive the desired conclusions.

Example 2: Let V be an n -dimensional vector space over the number field F . For any given positive integer $m \geq n$, there exist m vectors in V such that any n vectors among them are linearly independent.

Proof: Since $F \cong F^n$, therefore, it suffices to consider the problem within F^n .

$$a_1 = (1, 2, 2^2, \dots, 2^{n-1}),$$

$$a_2 = (1, 2, (2^2)^2, \dots, (2^{n-1})^2),$$

\vdots

$$a_m = (1, 2^m, (2^2)^m, \dots, (2^{n-1})^m).$$

Let

$$D_n = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2^{k_1} & (2^2)^{k_1} & \cdots & (2^{n-1})^{k_1} \\ 1 & 2^{k_2} & (2^2)^{k_2} & \cdots & (2^{n-1})^{k_2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 2^{k_n} & (2^2)^{k_n} & \cdots & (2^{n-1})^{k_n} \end{vmatrix}, 1 \leq k_1 \leq k_2 \leq \cdots \leq k_n \leq m,$$

since

$$D_n = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2^{k_1} & (2^{k_1})^2 & \cdots & (2^{k_1})^{n-1} \\ 1 & 2^{k_2} & (2^{k_2})^2 & \cdots & (2^{k_2})^{n-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 2^{k_n} & (2^{k_n})^2 & \cdots & (2^{k_n})^{n-1} \end{vmatrix}$$

is a Vandermonde determinant and $D_n \neq 0$, $a_{k_1}, a_{k_2}, a_{k_3}, \dots, a_{k_n}$ is linearly independent.

3.3 Applications of the Vandermonde Determinant in Polynomials

Example 3: Prove that if the n -th degree polynomial

$$f(x) = a_n + a_{n-1}x + a_{n-2}x^2 + \cdots + a_1x^{n-1} + a_0x^n$$

has $n+1$ distinct roots, then $f(x) \equiv 0$.

Proof: Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}$ be $n+1$ distinct roots of $f(x)$; then we have

$$\begin{cases} a_n + a_{n-1}x_1 + a_{n-2}x_1^2 + \cdots + a_1x_1^{n-1} + a_0x_1^n = 0 \\ a_n + a_{n-1}x_2 + a_{n-2}x_2^2 + \cdots + a_1x_2^{n-1} + a_0x_2^n = 0 \\ \vdots \\ a_n + a_{n-1}x_{n+1} + a_{n-2}x_{n+1}^2 + \cdots + a_1x_{n+1}^{n-1} + a_0x_{n+1}^n = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

This can be regarded as a homogeneous linear system consisting of $n+1$ unknowns (i.e., $a_n, a_{n-1}, \dots, a_1, a_0$,) and $n+1$ equations.

Its coefficient determinant can be expressed as

$$D_{n+1} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^n \\ 1 & x_2 & x_2^2 & \cdots & x_2^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_{n+1} & x_{n+1}^2 & \cdots & x_{n+1}^n \end{vmatrix} = \prod_{1 \leq j < i \leq n+1} (x_i - x_j) \neq 0.$$

Thus, we can conclude that Eq. (2) has only the trivial solution, i.e., $a_n = a_{n-1} = \cdots = a_1 = a_0 = 0$; in other words, $f(x) \equiv 0$.

3.4 Applications of the Vandermonde Determinant in Calculus

Example 4: Prove that there exists a unique n -th degree polynomial $p_n(x)$ such that $p_n(x) = y_i$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, n$).

Proof: Let $p_n(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \cdots + a_nx^n$, according to the given conditions, we have

$$\begin{cases} a_0 + a_1x_0 + a_2x_0^2 + \cdots + a_nx_0^n = y_0 \\ a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_1^2 + \cdots + a_nx_1^n = y_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_0 + a_1x_n + a_2x_n^2 + \cdots + a_nx_n^n = y_n \end{cases},$$

this is a linear system with a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n as the unknowns, and its coefficient determinant is the transpose of a Vandermonde determinant, i.e.,

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & x_0 & x_0^2 & \cdots & x_0^n \\ 1 & x_1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^n \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & \cdots & x_n^n \end{vmatrix} = \prod_{0 \leq i < j \leq n} (x_j - x_i).$$

Since $x_i \neq x_j (i \neq j)$, $D \neq 0$, thus, the linear system has a unique solution, i.e., there exists a unique polynomial $p_n(x)$ such that $p_n(x_i) = y_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, n)$.

4 Conclusion

As a crucial component of modern linear algebra, determinants include the Vandermonde determinant—a special type characterized by its unique structure and concise computational results. While its inherent conclusion is not overly complex, the core challenge in leveraging its application value lies in skillfully transforming a given determinant into the standard Vandermonde form. Such transformation demands considerable technical proficiency, requiring continuous summary, exploration, and refinement of its applicable rules in the learning process.

By exploring the comprehensive application of the Vandermonde determinant and related mathematical knowledge, this paper demonstrates advanced problem-solving skills that integrate theorems and properties, successfully addressing a variety of complex mathematical problems. This not only provides new directions for mathematics teaching and research but also reveals that in the problem-solving process, we must attach great importance to the inherent connections between knowledge points. Whether in future mathematics learning or exploration in other fields, we should encourage breaking through traditional solution methods,

continuously discovering and mastering flexible and efficient problem-solving ideas and techniques, thereby achieving genuine twice the result with half the effort.

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